

CHALLENGES WITH LISTENING AND SPEAKING SKILLS OF FUTURE INTERPRETERS

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ANNOTATION

Although simultaneous interpreting is a complex and demanding task, even isolated and relatively simple lexical units can pose a certain difficulty. The most important point is that novice interpreters are often confused when they have to focus on what is being said and speak simultaneously even if they do not need to analyse the meaning and context and logically connected utterances in the target language. One of the primary requirements for simultaneous interpreter is confident, clear and sufficiently loud speech, where logical stress is intonationally emphasized and pauses correspond to the norms of speech segmentation. In this article, we will discuss some of the common problems that can affect the listening and speaking skills of simultaneous interpreters.

Key words: *simultaneous interpreting, concentration, misunderstanding, feedback, language learning apps, nuances, novice interpreters, language classes, speaking skills.*

Future simultaneous interpreters' problems related to their listening and speaking skills. One of the primary challenges faced by future interpreters is the ability to listen and speak at the same time. Simultaneous interpreting requires the interpreter

to listen to the speaker and translate their words into another language in real-time. This requires a high level of concentration and the ability to process information quickly. However, many interpreters struggle with this task, as they find it difficult to keep up with the speaker's pace while also translating their words accurately. Another challenge faced by future interpreters is the ability to understand and interpret complex vocabulary and terminology. Many speakers use technical jargon and specialized vocabulary, which can be challenging for interpreters who are not familiar with the subject matter. This can lead to errors in the interpretation, which can have serious consequences in certain contexts, such as legal or medical settings. In addition to these challenges, future interpreters may also struggle with maintaining their focus and concentration for extended periods of time. Simultaneous interpreting can be mentally exhausting, as it requires the interpreter to maintain a high level of concentration for several hours at a time. This can lead to fatigue, which can affect their ability to listen and speak effectively. Moreover, future interpreters may also face challenges related to cultural differences and nuances in language. Interpreters must be aware of cultural differences and sensitivities, as well as differences in language usage and idiomatic expressions. Failure to understand these nuances can lead to misunderstandings and misinterpretations, which can have serious consequences in certain contexts.

How to overcome those problems mentioned above. Interpreting is a challenging profession that requires exceptional listening and speaking skills. Future interpreters often face difficulties in these areas, which can affect their performance and confidence. However, there are several strategies that can help them overcome these problems and improve their skills.

One of the most important skills for interpreters is active listening. This involves paying close attention to what the speaker is saying and asking questions for clarification. Future interpreters can practice active listening by listening to podcasts, lectures, or speeches in their target language and taking notes on the main points. They can also try summarizing what has been said to ensure they have understood it

correctly. Another key skill for interpreters is good pronunciation. Poor pronunciation can make it difficult for listeners to understand what they are saying, which can lead to misunderstandings. Future interpreters can work on improving their pronunciation by practicing speaking exercises, such as reading aloud, repeating phrases, and recording themselves speaking. Expanding vocabulary is also crucial for interpreters. They need to be able to understand and use a wide range of words and phrases in their target language. Future interpreters can expand their vocabulary by reading books, articles, and other materials in their target language and practicing using new words in context. Attending language classes can provide a structured environment for future interpreters to practice their listening and speaking skills. They can also receive feedback from teachers and classmates to help them improve. Seeking out opportunities to practice in real-world situations, such as attending events or meetings where their target language is spoken, can also be beneficial. Finally, using technology can aid learning. There are many language learning apps and tools available that can help future interpreters improve their listening and speaking skills. These include speech recognition software, flashcard apps, and language learning games.

In conclusion, future interpreters must be aware of the challenges they may face when performing simultaneous interpreting tasks. They must develop their listening and speaking skills, as well as their ability to understand complex vocabulary and cultural nuances. With proper training and practice, future interpreters can overcome these challenges and become effective communicators in a globalized world. Without interpreters, world summits would be unworkable and international business meetings impossible to conduct.

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